

GSPB theory for GCHS and QCPB theory for QCHS

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Abstract

In this note, we comprehensively sort out the theoretical system between the generalized structural Poisson bracket¹ (GSPB) theory for the generalized covariant Hamilton system (GCHS) and the quantum covariant Poisson bracket (QCPB) theory for quantum covariant Hamiltonian system (QCHS).

1 GSPB, GCHS, geometric bracket

To begin with the generalized Poisson bracket (GPB) that is defined as the bilinear operation

$$\{f, g\}_{GPB} = J_{ij} \partial_i f \partial_j g$$

where $\partial_i = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i}$, structural matrix J satisfies antisymmetric $J_{ij} = \{x_i, x_j\}_{GPB} = -J_{ji}$. Generalized Hamiltonian system (GHS) is defined by generalized Poisson bracket (GPB)

$$\dot{x}_i = \frac{dx_i}{dt} = \{x_i, H\}_{GPB} = J_{ij} \frac{\partial H}{\partial x_j}, \quad x \in \mathbb{R}^m \quad (1)$$

1.1 GSPB, GCHS

In this section, we briefly review some basic concepts of entire framework of GSPB theory. Let M be a smooth manifold and let s be a smooth real structural function on M which is completely determined by the structure of manifold M .

Theorem 1 (GSPB). [1] *The GSPB on M of two functions $f, g \in C^\infty(M, \mathbb{R})$ is defined as*

$$\{f, g\} = \{f, g\}_{GPB} + G(s, f, g)$$

for \mathbb{R}^r , the geometric bracket is

$$G(s, f, g) = f\{s, g\}_{GPB} - g\{s, f\}_{GPB}$$

in which s is structural function associated with M .

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¹GSPB: generalized structural Poisson bracket; GCHS: generalized covariant Hamilton system
QCPB: quantum covariant Poisson bracket; QCHS: quantum covariant Hamiltonian system.

Intuitively, one can understand this by realizing the second part geobacket $G(s, f, g)$. The GSPB

$$\begin{aligned}\{f, g\} &= \{f, g\}_{GPB} + G(s, f, g) \\ &= \{f, g\}_{GPB} + f\{s, g\}_{GPB} - g\{s, f\}_{GPB}\end{aligned}$$

which depends smoothly on both $\{f, g\}_{GPB}$ and the geobacket $G(s, f, g)$. Obviously, the geobacket $G(s, f, g)$ is necessary revision for a complete Hamiltonian system, as a result of the geobacket $G(s, f, g)$, it can be generally used to depict nonlinear system in a non-Euclidean space, and for general manifolds. As GSPB defined, the GCHS is completely ensured and determined by the GSPB. Therefore, the GCHS can be distinctly obtained as follows.

Theorem 2 (GCHS). [1] *The GCHS on M of two functions $f, H \in C^\infty(M, \mathbb{R})$ is defined as*

$$\frac{\mathcal{D}f}{dt} = \{f, H\} = \{f, H\}_{GPB} + G(s, f, H)$$

for \mathbb{R}^r , where geobacket in terms of f and Hamiltonian H is

$$G(s, f, H) = f\{s, H\}_{GPB} - H\{s, f\}_{GPB}$$

In fact, general covariance of the GCHS

$$\{f, H\} = \{f, H\}_{GPB} + f\{s, H\}_{GPB} - H\{s, f\}_{GPB}$$

holds naturally. The GCHS is totally dependent on the GSPB. Notice that the GCHS is completely covariant for the curved spacetime. Therefore, the motion is completely determined by the structure of the manifold M . This is also like the idea of general relativity where particles move on geodesics and the bending is caused by the gravity.

Theorem 3 (TGHS, S-dynamics, GCHS). [1]

TGHS: $\frac{df}{dt} = \dot{f} = \{f, H\}_{GPB} - H\{s, f\}_{GPB}$.

S-dynamics: $\frac{ds}{dt} = w = \{s, H\}_{GPB} = \{1, H\}$.

GCHS: $\frac{\mathcal{D}f}{dt} = \{f, H\} = \{f, H\}_{GPB} + G(s, f, H)$.

By defining the GSPB which can basically solve and describe an entire Hamiltonian system, even nonlinear system. Thus, in order to state this point. We explain that the GCHS corresponds to non-Euclidean space which corresponds to curved coordinate systems in curved spacetime. The geobacket $G(s, f, H)$ is the part that has been neglected for a long time which is rightly the correction term for the general covariance which certainly means nonlinear system. It is precise to see that the GCHS can describe and explain the generalized nonlinear system, the nonlinear Hamiltonian system.

In the following, the covariant equilibrium equation of the GCHS as a special case is naturally generated as follows.

Corollary 1. [1] *The covariant equilibrium equation of the GCHS is $\frac{Df}{dt} = \{f, H\} = 0$ such that*

$$\{f, H\}_{GSPB} + G(s, f, H) = 0$$

holds, where s is a structure function of the manifolds M , then f is called covariant conserved quantity.

1.2 Canonical covariant Hamilton equations

Corollary 2. [3] *The generalized force field F on the generalized Poisson manifold $(P, S, \{\cdot, \cdot\})$ is shown as*

$$F = \frac{d}{dt}p = -DH$$

Its components is $F_k = \dot{p}_k = -D_k H$.

Hence the GCHS can be naturally rewritten in the form

$$\frac{Df}{dt} = \{f, H\} = J_{ij} D_i f D_j H = J_{ji} F_j D_i f$$

Based on the GSPB, theoretically, we have the conservation of energy given by

$$\{H, H\} = J_{ij} F_i F_j = 0$$

in which $F_i = -D_i H$ is the components of generalized force F , and the TCHS is rewritten as

$$\dot{x}_k = J_{kj} D_j H = J_{jk} F_j$$

As concerned, by employing the generalized force field F , the GCHS also has the form given by

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{Df}{dt} &= \{f, H\} = -D^T f J F \\ &= -\nabla^T f J F - f \nabla^T s J F \\ &= J_{ji} D_i f F_j \\ &= J_{ji} F_j \partial_i f + f J_{ji} F_j \partial_i s \end{aligned}$$

Thusly, the TGHS and S-dynamics respectively are shown as

$$\begin{aligned} df/dt &= -\nabla^T f J F = J_{ji} F_j \partial_i f \\ ds/dt &= w = -\nabla^T s J F = J_{ji} F_j \partial_i s \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 4. [3] *There exists two different canonical Hamilton equations on manifolds respectively given by*

Canonical thorough Hamilton equations

$$\frac{dx_k}{dt} = \dot{x}_k = J_{jk} F_j, \quad \frac{dp_k}{dt} = \dot{p}_k = F_k$$

canonical covariant Hamilton equations

$$\frac{\mathcal{D}x_k}{dt} = \{x_k, H\}, \quad \frac{\mathcal{D}p_k}{dt} = \{p_k, H\}$$

where $\{\cdot, \cdot\} = \{\cdot, \cdot\}_{GPB} + G(s, \cdot, \cdot)$ is the GSPB.

As we can see, there is a relation for canonical thorough Hamilton equations given by $\dot{x}_k = J_{jk}\dot{p}_j$.

Corollary 3. [3] *The ordinary time derivative d/dt and covariant time operator \mathcal{D}/dt can be respectively rewritten in a form*

$$d/dt = \dot{x}_i \partial_i$$

$$\mathcal{D}/dt = \dot{x}_i D_i$$

where \dot{x}_i is the TGHS in terms of x_i , and then for the generalized force field F , we get

$$dp_k/dt = F_k = \dot{x}_i \partial_i p_k = \dot{x}_i \xi_{ik}$$

in terms of the momentum, where $\partial_i p_k = \xi_{ik}$. Similarly, for the S-dynamics, it yields

$$ds/dt = w = \dot{x}_i \partial_i s = \dot{x}_i A_i \tag{2}$$

in terms of the structure function s , and the TGHS is given by

$$df/dt = \dot{x}_i \partial_i f$$

for any function f .

Note that the S-dynamics expressed by (2) implies the relation between the structure derivative A_i and the S-dynamics itself, the S-dynamics is only induced by the structure derivative A_i , and based on the manifolds itself.

2 Generalized geometric commutator and geomutator

Let a and b be any two operators, their commutator is formally defined by $[a, b]_{cr} = ab - ba$. Let a and b be any elements of any algebra, or any operators, their generalized geometric commutator is formally defined by the following.

Definition 1 (GGC). [2] *A generalized geometric commutator (GGC) of arity two a, b is formally given by*

$$[a, b] = [a, b]_{cr} + G(s, a, b)$$

The geomutator is

$$G(s, a, b) = a[s, b]_{cr} - b[s, a]_{cr}$$

satisfying $G(s; a, b) = -G(s, b, a)$, where s is a geometric structure function given by domain.

As above definition given, the generalized geometric commutator (GGC)

$$[a, b] = [a, b]_{cr} + a[s, b]_{cr} - b[s, a]_{cr}$$

contains three parts. Some properties of the geomutator are given by

$$\begin{aligned} G(s, a + b, c + d) &= G(s, a, c) + G(s, b, d) + G(s, b, c) + G(s, a, d) \\ G(s, a + b, c) &= G(s, a, c) + G(s, b, c) \\ G(s, a, c + d) &= G(s, a, c) + G(s, a, d) \end{aligned}$$

for operators a, b, c, d . With some particular properties are given by

$$\begin{aligned} G(s, a, a) &= G(s, s, s) = 0 \\ G(s, s, a) &= s[s, a]_{cr} \\ G(s, a, s) &= s[a, s]_{cr} \end{aligned}$$

Definition 2. [2] *The covariant equilibrium equation is given by $[a, b] = 0$, i.e.,*

$$[a, b]_{cr} + G(s, a, b) = 0$$

for arbitrary operators a, b .

2.1 The QCPB theory and quantum geometric bracket

In this section, we begin with some basic concepts of quantum covariant Poisson bracket (QCPB) defined by the generalized geometric commutator (GGC), and quantum geometric bracket is defined by the geomutator. In quantum mechanics, the quantum Poisson brackets (QPB) $[\hat{f}, \hat{g}]_{QPB}$ is the commutator of two operators \hat{f}, \hat{g} defined as $[\hat{f}, \hat{g}]_{QPB} = \hat{f}\hat{g} - \hat{g}\hat{f}$.

Definition 3 (QCPB). [2] *The QCPB is generally defined as*

$$[\hat{f}, \hat{g}] = [\hat{f}, \hat{g}]_{QPB} + G(s, \hat{f}, \hat{g})$$

in terms of quantum operator \hat{f}, \hat{g} , where $G(s, \hat{f}, \hat{g}) = -G(s, \hat{g}, \hat{f})$ is called quantum geometric bracket.

It is zero if and only if \hat{f} and \hat{g} covariant commute, i.e. $[\hat{f}, \hat{g}] = 0$. It is remarkable to see that the QCPB representation admits a dynamical geometric bracket formula on the manifold. Note that structural function s represents the background property of spacetime.

Definition 4 (quantum geometric bracket). [2] *The quantum geometric bracket is*

$$G(s, \hat{f}, \hat{g}) = \hat{f}[s, \hat{g}]_{QPB} - \hat{g}[s, \hat{f}]_{QPB}$$

where s represents the globally condition of space.

As a consequence of the precise formulation of the quantum geometric bracket, the QCPB is completely written as

$$\left[\hat{f}, \hat{g} \right] = \left[\hat{f}, \hat{g} \right]_{QPB} + \hat{f}[s, \hat{g}]_{QPB} - \hat{g}[s, \hat{f}]_{QPB}$$

Definition 5. [2] *The covariant equilibrium equation is given by $\left[\hat{f}, \hat{g} \right] = 0$, i.e.,*

$$\left[\hat{f}, \hat{g} \right]_{QPB} + G(s, \hat{f}, \hat{g}) = 0$$

for operators \hat{f} , \hat{g} .

3 Quantum covariant Hamiltonian system

This section will give the covariant dynamics which contains two different dynamics: the generalized Heisenberg equation and G-dynamics. It tells that the generalized Heisenberg equation perfects the Heisenberg equation by considering the structural function s . Firstly, let's give the definition of quantum covariant Hamiltonian system (QCHS) defined by the QCPB as definition 3 shown.

In the beginning, let us start with the QCPB by taking $\hat{g} = \hat{H}$ into consideration, then it formally yields below definition.

Definition 6 (QCHS). [2] *The QCHS defined by QCPB in terms of quantum operator \hat{f} , \hat{H} is generally given by*

$$\left[\hat{f}, \hat{H} \right] = \left[\hat{f}, \hat{H} \right]_{QPB} + G(s, \hat{f}, \hat{H})$$

where $G(s, \hat{f}, \hat{H})$ is quantum geobacket in terms of the operators \hat{f} , \hat{H} .

Thusly, the quantum geobacket $G(s, \hat{f}, \hat{H})$ is precisely defined as

Definition 7. [2] *The quantum geobacket for a Hamiltonian operator \hat{H} is given by*

$$G(s, \hat{f}, \hat{H}) = \hat{f}[s, \hat{H}]_{QPB} - \hat{H}[s, \hat{f}]_{QPB}$$

and s is a real structural function only associated with the structure space.

Manifestly, this operator \hat{f} covariantly commutes with H . By our construction, the QCHS derived from the QCPB is a transition for the further development of a complete and covariant theory that can naturally generalize the Heisenberg equation. Since \hat{f} is an observable, s is assumed to be real function as well.

Definition 8. [2] *The covariant equilibrium equation is given by $\left[\hat{f}, \hat{H} \right] = 0$, i.e.,*

$$\left[\hat{f}, \hat{H} \right]_{QPB} + G(s, \hat{f}, \hat{H}) = 0$$

for operators \hat{f} , \hat{H} , then \hat{f} is called quantum covariant conserved quantity.

Furthermore, there is a certain case given by

$$\left[\hat{H}, \hat{H} \right] = -\hat{H} \left[s, \hat{H} \right]_{QPB} + \hat{H} \left[s, \hat{H} \right]_{QPB} = 0 \quad (3)$$

when $\hat{f} = \hat{H}$ based on definition 8. It is clear to see that \hat{H} is a quantum covariant conserved quantity.

3.1 Covariant dynamics, generalized Heisenberg equation, G-dynamics

In this section, we will briefly review the entire theoretical framework of quantum covariant Hamiltonian system

$$\left[\hat{f}, \hat{H} \right] = \left[\hat{f}, \hat{H} \right]_{QPB} + \hat{f} \left[s, \hat{H} \right]_{QPB} - \hat{H} \left[s, \hat{f} \right]_{QPB}$$

defined by the quantum covariant Poisson bracket. More precisely, the time covariant evolution of any observable \hat{f} in the covariant dynamics is given by both the generalized Heisenberg equation of motion and G-dynamics.

Theorem 5 (The covariant dynamics). [2] *The covariant dynamics, the generalized Heisenberg equation, G-dynamics can be formally formulated as*

The covariant dynamics: $\frac{\mathcal{D}\hat{f}}{dt} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{-1}\hbar} \left[\hat{f}, \hat{H} \right]$

The generalized Heisenberg equation: $\frac{d\hat{f}}{dt} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{-1}\hbar} \left[\hat{f}, \hat{H} \right]_{QPB} - \frac{1}{\sqrt{-1}\hbar} \hat{H} \left[s, \hat{f} \right]_{QPB}$

G-dynamics: $\hat{w} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{-1}\hbar} \left[s, \hat{H} \right]_{QPB}$.

respectively, where $\frac{\mathcal{D}}{dt} = \frac{d}{dt} + \hat{w}$ is covariant time operator, and \hat{H} is the Hamiltonian and $[\cdot, \cdot]$ denotes the GGC of two operators.

Based on the G-dynamics, the imaginary geomenergy can be completely defined, we can better give a presentation for the covariant dynamics, ect.

Definition 9. [2] *The imaginary geomenergy is defined by*

$$E^{(\text{Im})}(\hat{w}) = \sqrt{-1}\hbar\hat{w} = \left[s, \hat{H} \right]_{QPB}$$

where \hat{w} is the G-dynamics.

It is obvious that the imaginary geomenergy can be expressed as

$$E^{(\text{Im})}(\hat{w}) = \sqrt{-1}\hbar\hat{w} = \left[s, \hat{H} \right]_{QPB}$$

Thus, a dynamical variable \hat{f} with the geomenergy defined above, then covariant dynamics is rewritten in the form

$$\sqrt{-1}\hbar \frac{\mathcal{D}}{dt} \hat{f} = [\hat{f}, \hat{H}] = \sqrt{-1}\hbar \frac{d}{dt} \hat{f} + \hat{f} E^{(\text{Im})}(\hat{w})$$

As a consequence of the imaginary geomenergy, we can say that imaginary geomenergy is a new kind of Hamiltonian operator. Obviously, if the covariant equilibrium equation $[\hat{f}, \hat{H}] = 0$ holds, then it yields

$$\frac{d}{dt} \hat{f} + \hat{f} \hat{w} = 0$$

or this covariant equilibrium formula in the form shows $\frac{d}{dt} \hat{f} = -\hat{f} \hat{w}$, accordingly, \hat{f} is said to be a quantum covariant conserved quantity.

4 The GSPB theory and the QCPB theory

Recall that the relation of the GSPB theory and the QCPB theory, clearly, they are used for two different realms, classically and quantum fields. [see [2] for more details].

In totally, we emphasize that the GSPB in a precise form is given as definition shown

$$\{f, g\} = \{f, g\}_{GSPB} + G(s, f, g)$$

While the QCPB is taken the same pattern as a quantum correspondence,

$$[\hat{f}, \hat{g}] = [\hat{f}, \hat{g}]_{QPB} + G(s, \hat{f}, \hat{g})$$

This is as a similar pattern for classical and quantum brackets in the view of the relation between quantum mechanics and classic mechanics. Notice that in this representation the fundamental equations are similar to the classical equations with the substitution.

$$\begin{aligned} \{f, g\} &= \{f, g\}_{GSPB} + G(s, f, g) \\ \mapsto \frac{1}{\sqrt{-1}\hbar} [\hat{f}, \hat{g}] &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{-1}\hbar} \left([\hat{f}, \hat{g}]_{QPB} + G(s, \hat{f}, \hat{g}) \right) \end{aligned}$$

With the solid foundation of the GSPB and the QCPB generally, then the covariant dynamical equation certainly follows based on the GSPB and the QCPB respectively. From the GCHS

$$\frac{\mathcal{D}f}{dt} = \{f, H\} = \{f, H\}_{GSPB} + G(s, f, H)$$

to the quantum covariant dynamics. Furthermore, the covariant equation of the motion of an arbitrary operator \hat{f} or the observables \hat{f} that satisfies the quantum covariant evolution

$$\frac{\mathcal{D}\hat{f}}{dt} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{-1}\hbar} [\hat{f}, \hat{H}] = \frac{1}{\sqrt{-1}\hbar} \left([\hat{f}, \hat{H}]_{QPB} + G(s, \hat{f}, \hat{H}) \right)$$

Namely, the time covariant evolution of the operator \hat{f} is then given by the corresponding equation

$$\frac{\mathcal{D}f}{dt} = \{f, H\} \rightarrow \frac{\mathcal{D}\hat{f}}{dt} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{-1}\hbar} [\hat{f}, \hat{H}]$$

This specifically shows

$$\begin{pmatrix} GHS \\ QHS \end{pmatrix} \xrightarrow{+G(s, \cdot, \cdot)} \begin{pmatrix} GCHS \\ QCHS \end{pmatrix}$$

More specifically, the formulations between the GSPB and the QCPB can be listed as follows,

The GSPB and the QCPB:

$$\begin{aligned} \{f, g\} &= \{f, g\}_{GPB} + G(s, f, g) \\ [\hat{f}, \hat{g}] &= [\hat{f}, \hat{g}]_{QPB} + G(s, \hat{f}, \hat{g}) \end{aligned}$$

It is clear to see that the GSPB and the QCPB as the grand new tool for us better understanding the physical process precisely.

$$\begin{pmatrix} GPB \\ QPB \end{pmatrix} \xrightarrow{+G(s, \cdot, \cdot)} \begin{pmatrix} GSPB \\ QCPB \end{pmatrix}$$

As a consequence, the equations of motion are respectively obtained by applying generalized Heisenberg equations of motion and canonical quantum covariant Hamilton equations.

Next, we put the geobacket and quantum geobacket together to contrastively analyze their connections. Especially, the covariant correction terms—the geobacket $G(s, f, g)$ and the quantum geobacket $G(s, \hat{f}, \hat{g})$. As described previously, the geobacket $G(s, f, g)$ in GSPB is defined as

$$G(s, f, g) = f\{s, g\}_{GPB} - g\{s, f\}_{GPB}$$

In a similar mode for quantum mechanics, quantum geobacket $G(s, \hat{f}, \hat{g})$ can be basically concretized in QCPB, that is given by

$$G(s, \hat{f}, \hat{g}) = \hat{f}[s, \hat{g}]_{QPB} - \hat{g}[s, \hat{f}]_{QPB}$$

Note that the structure function s is a scalar function only associated with the spatial structure, its precise form is determined by the space we study, such as on the Riemann manifold, it takes $s = \ln \sqrt{g}$. In order to better understand this scalar function, it's similar to the Kähler potential.

In conclusions, the complete theory for general Hamiltonian problems should take the latter form

$$GPB \Rightarrow GSPB, \quad GHS \Rightarrow GCHS$$

in another form, the GSPB, GCHS are the complete form to describe the non-linear Hamiltonian problems. In the field of the quantum mechanics, the corresponding complete quantum theory is also a replacement given by

$$\text{QPB} \Rightarrow \text{QCPB}, \quad \text{QHS} \Rightarrow \text{QCHS}$$

It means that QCPB, QCHS has widely depicted the general quantum problems, including the gravity.

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